

Spontaneous Rupture of the Spleen

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Abstract

Ruptures of the spleen that are not caused by trauma are rare, difficult to diagnose and potentially fatal. They occur in the absence of any trauma. This case report presents a spontaneous rupture of the spleen, highlighting the diagnostic and therapeutic challenges it poses. The authors report the case of a 24-year-old male smoker who consulted them for sudden pain in the left hypochondrium that radiated to the shoulder (Kehr's sign), which was associated with hypovolaemic shock. Biological work-up revealed acute anemia, and abdominal CT scan showed splenic rupture with unexpected hemoperitoneum. The patient was managed conservatively in an intensive care unit with clinical and biological monitoring, without surgical intervention. This case highlights the importance of early evaluation of an atypical acute abdominal presentation essentially in the absence of obvious trauma and which can rapidly engage the vital prognosis in the absence of an optimal diagnostic and therapeutic approach.

More Information

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Introduction

Spontaneous rupture of the spleen is rare, with a non-negligible mortality rate, and its diagnosis is often delayed in the absence of a traumatic context. It is a medico-surgical emergency that has been reported in several cases in the literature [1,2]. It has also been described in various pathological situations, mainly infectious. It can occur in a normal spleen in a patient without risk factors [3] or in a pathological spleen, such as a tumor [4]. We report a new case of spontaneous rupture of the spleen, managed in the P33 surgical emergency resuscitation department of CHU Ibn Rochd in Casablanca.

Case Presentation

A 24-year-old patient, known to be a smoker with 8 pack-years, with no particular history, was referred to the emergency department for sudden onset of diffuse abdominal pain. His symptoms began 48 h before admission with pain in the left hypochondrium. Abdominal ultrasonography showed a heterogeneous echogenic patch in the splenic lodge, peritoneal effusion around the liver, in the parietocolic gutters and in the CDS of Douglas. The abdominal CT scan evoked the diagnosis of ruptured spleen, confirming the existence of moderate hemoperitoneum and a ruptured splenic subcapsular hematoma (see Figure 1).

Figure 1: Ruptured Splenic Subcapsular Hematoma Complicated by Large-Sclae Hemoperitoneum on Abdominal CT Scan

Due to hemodynamic stability and the absence of active bleeding, the patient was treated conservatively in the intensive care unit p33, no surgical intervention was necessary, the patient was closely monitored for hemodynamic stability, and treatment included strict bed rest, intravenous hydration, analgesia, red blood cell transfusion, and antibiotic prophylaxis. The patient's condition improved significantly, with a marked reduction in pain under level 1 analgesia. Laboratory tests every 12 hours showed stabilization of hemoglobin without worsening of anemia, which remained at around 9.3 g/dl vs. 7.8 g/dl on the first day. No signs of complications were noted. After hemodynamic stabilization and on the fourth day, the patient was transferred from intensive care to a regular ward, with a follow-up CT scan scheduled.

Discussion

Spontaneous rupture of the spleen is a rare but potentially fatal condition that requires rigorous exploration of any acute abdominal presentation with rapid diagnosis and an appropriate therapeutic strategy even in the absence of trauma, which often makes diagnosis difficult and delayed. In our case, the patient had no previous trauma or underlying pathology, which confirms its idiopathic nature. In a study by Schwarz and Zaidenstein, an adolescent with infectious mononucleosis, treated conservatively by progressive percutaneous drainage of a subcapsular hematoma, showed that non-surgical treatment could be envisaged [5]. Malaria may be one of the documented causes; the study by Mokashi et al. reports a case of splenic rupture on a pathological spleen due to malaria, which presented with an acute abdomen with hemodynamic instability, requiring splenectomy [6]. In our case, the patient was healthy, with no infectious or hematological context, unlike this study where the patient was infected with Plasmodium and presented a more critical picture. The study by Massarweh and Dhingra [4] reports a rare case of isolated splenic metastasis of lung cancer complicated by spontaneous rupture of the spleen, the tumoral context imposing a particular therapeutic strategy and specific oncological treatment. The friable nature of the tumor is incriminated in the hemorrhagic context which requires recourse to splenectomy. Spontaneous rupture of the spleen can be a rare and severe complication of acute pancreatitis. Diagnosis relies on imaging to detect subcapsular hematomas, and treatment ranging from strict surveillance to splenectomy or arterial embolization [7]. In our case, splenic capsule embrittlement is idiopathic, whereas in the Habib et al. study, embrittlement is due to inflammation and pancreatic enzymes. Management depends mainly on the patient's hemodynamic stability, Rapp et al. report three cases of splenic rupture linked to infections,

analyzing the therapeutic choice between splenectomy and conservative treatment [8]. If the patient is stable, the non-surgical approach is the most widely used, as our case shows. Splenic arterial embolization is an interventional technique increasingly used in hemodynamically stable patients. This conservative approach preserves the immunological function of the spleen, and prevents postsplenectomy infections. A case of splenic artery embolization in a patient with acute promyelocytic leukemia has demonstrated the value of this technique in immunodepressed patients in protecting the immune system and reducing postoperative infectious complications [9]. Spontaneous rupture of the spleen without trauma or underlying pathology is a rare entity, often diagnosed late. Our case highlights that strictly conservative management based on careful clinical and radiological monitoring can lead to a favorable outcome in a stable patient. It also highlights the importance of adapting treatment to the clinical context, thus avoiding invasive procedures such as surgery or embolization.

Conclusion

Spontaneous rupture of the spleen is potentially rare, requiring individualized management adapted to the clinical picture. The absence of trauma should not rule out this diagnostic hypothesis. This case highlights the importance of rapid diagnosis and rigorous follow-up, guided mainly by imaging and clinical status.

Ethical Statement

Consent for treatment and open access publication was obtained or waived by all participants in this study.

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